

IMPACT: An Unplugged Board Game to Introduce Programming

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WHAT IS IMPACT ?

IMPACT (Informative Mini-Games for Programming concepts and Computational Thinking) tackles a **key gap** in Swiss primary education: fundamental programming concepts and Computational Thinking are not sufficiently taught in grades 3 and 4 ¹. This often leads to difficulties when students encounter programming for the first time in grade 5.

To address this, IMPACT developed an **unplugged board game that introduces programming principles** such as sequences, loops, and conditions in a playful, age-appropriate way. Using an Educational Design Research (EDR) approach (Plomp, 2013), the game was iteratively refined through literature reviews, teacher interviews, and expert feedback. The first classroom tests showed that the game is intuitive, adaptable, and aligns well with curriculum goals. Teachers highlighted its potential to ease the transition to coding environments. IMPACT shows how unplugged, game-based learning can build foundational skills early and support a smoother start into programming. Future steps include broader testing, training modules for teachers, and further development based on classroom experience.

¹ <https://zh.lehrplan.ch/index.php?code=hl10102>

OBJECTIVES

This project aims to support the early development of programming competencies in 4th grade by designing and evaluating an unplugged, game-based learning approach. The main objectives are:

- ✓ Design a board game to teach basic programming concepts playfully.
- ✓ Evaluate usability, acceptance, and educational potential in schools.
- ✓ Develop and refine the prototype following the Educational Design Research (EDR) approach.

REFERENCES

Plomp, T. (2013) 'Educational design research: An introduction', Educational Design Research, pp. 11–50.

Tsarava, K., Moeller, K. and Ninaus, M. (2019) 'Board games for training computational thinking', in Gentile, M., Allegra, M. and Söbke, H. (eds) Games and Learning Alliance. Cham: Springer International Publishing, pp. 90–100. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978->

Tsarava, K., Moeller, K. and Ninaus, M. (2018) 'Training computational thinking through board games: The case of Crabs & Turtles', International Journal of Serious Games, 5(2), pp. 25–44.

PROJECT PHASE 1

Expert Interviews

Expert interviews with four teachers who later participated in the classroom pilot

Testing by Didactics Experts

Their feedback led to further refinement of the game prior to the intervention phase

1

Literature Review

Analysis of existing board games (e.g. Tsarava et al. 2018 & 2019)

2

Prototype Development

- Game board and game cards
- Two to four players control avatars across a game board using command cards to collect coins placed at the corners of the board
- Several levels covering programming concepts such as loops, conditions, sequences, and events

3

4

Testing in Classroom

- 161 grade 4 students from eight classes in the cantons of Zurich and Schwyz
- Focus group interviews with students
- Student survey to assess game experience

5

RESULTS & FUTURE WORK

Collected Data Sets:

- Qualitative data from audio recordings of student focus group interviews
- Quantitative survey data on game experience
- Qualitative data from teacher post-interview recordings

Initial Insights:

While final data analysis is still pending, several initial findings can be reported: Implementation was successful in all classes. Students understood the rules and could play independently or with minor support. The physical design—coins, cards—was appealing. Game mechanics functioned well, e.g., the balance of card types, board size, and coin quantity supported progress and achievements. Three out of six levels were tested during the pilot.

Teachers gave consistently positive feedback in interviews. They found the game age-appropriate and noted observable learning effects. All participating classes kept a prototype and all teachers expressed interest in using the game again.

Project Phase 2

(IMPACT+ funded by Haslerstiftung 2025-2026):

A comprehensive **analysis of the dataset** will be conducted using both qualitative and quantitative methods. These findings will guide targeted revisions.

A **hybrid version will be developed together with inlusio.com**. This will include a narrative-driven digital layer, offering contextual support without being essential to gameplay.

The board game will be complemented by teacher guides, optional challenges, and lesson ideas. All printable game components will be made available as **Open Educational Resources (OER)**.

The next **classroom study** will involve 2–4 classes to test the hybrid version's usability, clarity of narrative elements, and pedagogical effectiveness.

Project Phase 3

Future research will explore how unplugged learning with the game facilitates the **transition to visual programming environments** such as Scratch. A comparative study will evaluate the **learning gains**.

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Read Full Paper

<https://tiny.phzh.ch/impact-2025>